

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

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Abbreviations list

API	Application Programming Interface
DMP	Data Management Plan
EOSC	European Open Science cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
IF	Interoperability Framework
IF/RA	Interoperability Framework/Reference Architecture
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PID	Persistent Identifier
PTA	Plan-Track-Assess
RA	Reference Architecture
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RUP	Rational Unified Process
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service

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Executive Summary

The OSTrails project focuses on developing and adopting an Interoperability Framework (IF) designed to integrate Data Management Plan (DMP) platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), FAIR assessment tools, and other research-supporting services. Central to this effort is the OSTrails Commons (referred to also as ‘the Commons’ hereafter), a set of open, reusable specifications that simplify the inclusion of tools into the federation of interoperable services. This framework aims to support seamless collaboration among tools while remaining flexible for future integrations.

The current challenge lies in defining the Commons, a resource set that facilitates practical implementation while remaining tool-agnostic. As the first iteration of the Commons, this deliverable focuses on specifying the core concepts, coverage, features, and structure of the Commons. It also explores considerations necessary for aligning with inter-project and international standards to ensure broader applicability. This will serve as a blueprint for building the Commons (towards Deliverable 2.6 and beyond).

This document specifies the scope and structure of the Commons, outlines its primary components, and establishes their technical and social dimensions. It also aligns these specifications with European and global initiatives to foster interoperability. This groundwork prepares the federation for seamless integration of existing and future tools, ensuring scalability and compliance.

A structured approach, informed by Software Engineering principles and the Rational Unified Process (RUP), was used to design the Commons. Analysis from earlier project deliverables, especially D2.1, guided decisions regarding technologies and requirements. Global frameworks such as the Research Data Alliance’s Global Open Research Commons (GORC) influenced the design, ensuring alignment with international best practices across technical and social dimensions.

This report details the definition and structure of the Commons, discusses its European and global context (using the GORC international model), and then describes technical realisation plans. Finally, a roadmap for developing the Commons is also included, setting the stage for their implementation in the project's next phases.

1. Methodology

The methodology for developing the Commons focuses on a structured, iterative approach that ensures integration within the OSTrails ecosystem while aligning with international frameworks like GORC and EOSC. This approach combines established software engineering practices with insights from prior project deliverables to guide the definition and realisation of the Commons.

1.1. Software Engineering Approach

The development of the Commons draws on established software engineering methodologies, combining the structured, phase-based approach of the Rational Unified Process (RUP)¹ with the flexibility and responsiveness of agile methodologies². This dual approach accommodates the unique nature of the project, which involves defining reusable specifications rather than building a standalone software product.

The Rational Unified Process provides a framework for iterative development, enabling systematic progress through phases tailored to the current goals. For the specification phase of the Commons, the RUP phases (see [Figure 1](#)) are applied as follows:

- **Inception Phase:**
 - During this phase, the focus is on consolidating findings from Deliverable 2.1, which analysed tools and related technologies.
 - Core objectives and the scope of the Commons are identified, with an emphasis on ensuring alignment with the broader interoperability framework of OSTrails.
 - Stakeholder input is gathered to validate priorities and refine high-level requirements for the Commons.
- **Elaboration Phase:**
 - The current phase focuses on refining the Commons' architecture and specifications based on iterative feedback and deeper analysis.
 - Key deliverables include detailed definitions of core components, their relationships to the OSTrails Interoperability Framework, and alignment with European and global standards (e.g., GORC, EOSC).
 - Agile principles are applied here to maintain flexibility and ensure responsiveness to the evolving needs of tools and their integration processes.
- **Construction and Transition Phases (Future):**
 - Once the Commons is well-defined, iterative development will continue in coordination with the OSTrails tools.

¹ Philippe Kruchten (2003). *The Rational Unified Process: An Introduction*, ISBN: 978-0321197702

² Humble Jez, Farley David (2022). *Modern Software Engineering*, ISBN: 978-0137314911

- Incremental implementation and testing of Commons components will ensure practical alignment with the interoperability goals and scalability of the ecosystem.
- During the transition phase, the focus will shift to deployment, feedback integration, and continuous improvement based on real-world use cases.

While RUP provides a structured backbone, agile methodologies are essential to ensure the iterative and collaborative nature of the Commons' development. Agile principles will guide both the specification and realisation phases through:

- **Iterative Cycles:** Specifications will evolve through short, iterative cycles that incorporate feedback from tool developers and other stakeholders. This iterative approach ensures that the Commons remains practical and adaptable.
- **Stakeholder Collaboration:** Active engagement with tool developers, interoperability experts, and other stakeholders to refine specifications and ensure alignment with real-world needs.
- **Incremental Deliverables:** Delivering modular, usable specifications in each iteration to support early adoption and iterative testing.

Figure 1 - Rational Unified Process phases (source: testbytes.net)

The iterative and agile nature of this approach ensures that the Commons evolves alongside the tools it supports. Realisation of the Commons will occur in parallel with ongoing tool development, prototyping, and interoperability enhancements, creating a dynamic feedback loop where insights from the specification phase will guide practical implementation, and challenges with related experience with implementation in specific tools (DMP platforms, SKGs, and FAIR assessment tools) will inform updates to the specifications.

1.2. Intra-OSTrails Relations

The development of the Commons is deeply embedded within the structured progression of the OSTrails project, relying on the interconnected deliverables and milestones that collectively define the project's trajectory. This interdependency ensures that the

Commons is not only aligned with the current needs of the federation but also anticipates and supports future advancements.

The Commons builds upon the groundwork laid by earlier deliverables, such as the **Plan-Track-Assess Pathways (D1.1)**, which specified the foundational relationships between tools in the OSTrails framework. These pathways provided a clear map of how tools interact to facilitate research workflows, offering valuable context for designing the Commons to enable seamless integration. Similarly, the **FAIRness Reference Model for Digital Objects V1 (D1.2)** and the **OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V1 (D1.4)** introduce guiding principles and technical structures that inform the Commons' specifications. These deliverables ensure that the Commons aligns with the overarching goal of promoting FAIR data practices and robust interoperability across the federation.

A critical input to the Commons' design is the **Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance (D2.1)**, which assessed the current interoperability practices, technological choices, and readiness of tools within the OSTrails federation. This analysis highlighted gaps and opportunities, serving as the basis for prioritising features and determining how the Commons can address practical challenges faced by tools. Feedback loops from ongoing updates and pilot implementations, such as those delivered in **OSTrails Software and Services V1 (D2.2)**, enable iterative refinement of the Commons to ensure its practicality and usability in real-world scenarios.

Figure 2 - Relations between OSTrails Commons-related Deliverables and Milestones

Looking forward, the OSTrails Commons is not merely an intermediate output; it plays a pivotal role in shaping the federation's continued evolution. The Commons will guide future iterations of tools, supporting implementation efforts in **D2.3** and **D2.4** as these deliverables introduce V2 and V3 of OSTrails software and services within the federation. Furthermore, its specifications and insights will feed into the next version of the **OSTrails Interoperability Reference Architecture V2 (D1.5)**, ensuring that the entire framework evolves in alignment with real-world needs and emerging technologies. This

interconnected development process is supported by milestones such as the **Interim Products Establishment (Milestone 4)**, which provided a foundation for the Commons' early design, and the **Preliminary Analysis Results (Milestone 5)**, which further informed its scope and structure. Key of these dependencies as visualized in **Figure 2**.

The Commons is essential for connecting the specification phase with the practical implementation of tools within the OSTrails federation, enabling a feedback loop where the tools both inform and benefit from the Commons' development. However, its purpose extends beyond the immediate federation. It must be designed to serve as a reusable and adaptable resource for tools outside the OSTrails ecosystem and for future projects that may adopt its interoperability framework. This dual focus ensures the Commons not only addresses internal needs but also contributes to **broader global and cross-project interoperability efforts**.

Through this dynamic exchange of inputs and outputs, the Commons exemplify the project's iterative methodology, informed by real-world tool analysis and feedback from pilot implementations. This integration of past deliverables, ongoing updates, and future plans ensures that it is not only a product of its dependencies but also a driver of the federation's future growth and interoperability.

1.3. Influences from GORC and EOSC

The development of the Commons is informed by global and regional frameworks that provide guiding principles and best practices for building interoperable and scalable research infrastructures. Two key influences are the **RDA Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model** and the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Interoperability Framework**. These initiatives shape the methodology by emphasising alignment with global standards, fostering interoperability, and ensuring flexibility to accommodate diverse tools and services.

The GORC model offers a global perspective, addressing the challenges and opportunities of federating research commons across countries and disciplines. Its influence on the Commons methodology includes:

- **Functional Alignment:** Identifying core areas such as data management, computational infrastructure, and tools/services integration, which are essential for ensuring the Commons is realisable and supports a wide range of research activities.
- **Global Interoperability:** Encouraging the adoption of shared protocols and APIs to enable seamless interaction between OSTrails ecosystem and other research commons worldwide.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Promoting modular design and flexible architectures to support the evolving needs of tools and emerging technologies.
- **Social and Technical Balance:** Highlighting the importance of addressing both technical interoperability and the social dimensions of collaboration, such as governance and stakeholder engagement.

The GORC's emphasis on inclusivity and adaptability ensures that the Commons can serve as a reusable resource across international contexts, enhancing its relevance and impact.

On the other hand, the EOSC Interoperability Framework³ provides specific guidelines for federating research services and infrastructures within the European context. Its influence on the Commons methodology includes:

- **Layered Interoperability:** Structuring the Commons around technical, semantic, organisational, and legal layers to address the full spectrum of interoperability requirements.
- **FAIR Principles:** Ensuring that data, tools, and services associated with the Commons adhere to the principles of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, aligning with EOSC's objectives.
- **Standardisation:** Leveraging EOSC recommendations for metadata schemas, APIs, and other technical standards to facilitate integration with European research infrastructures.
- **Federated Ecosystem:** Adopting a federated approach that allows the Commons to operate as a decentralised yet connected resource, similar to the EOSC ecosystem.

By combining insights from GORC and EOSC, the Commons methodology achieves a balance between global relevance and regional specificity. Best practices from both models ensure compatibility with European and global research infrastructures, while an iterative approach inspired by GORC's adaptability and EOSC's guidelines allows the Commons to evolve alongside tools and interoperability mechanisms. Furthermore, the methodology emphasises stakeholder collaboration, integrating feedback to ensure the Commons remains practical and widely adoptable. This dual influence positions the Commons as both technically robust and strategically aligned with European and global research initiatives.

³ <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

2. OSTrails Commons Definition

The **OSTrails Commons** is formally defined as a collection of open, reusable, and adaptable resources that collectively enable and enhance interoperability within the OSTrails ecosystem and beyond. These resources are designed to **lower adoption barriers** to integration by standardising interactions between tools, ensuring alignment with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF) and Reference Architecture (RA). The Commons is **not standalone tools or services**; rather, they provide the **foundational elements that support and guide the development, operation, and evolution** of interoperable research-supporting platforms. By bridging technical, semantic, and procedural gaps, the Commons facilitate collaboration and scalability while remaining flexible for adaptation to emerging technologies and diverse research contexts.

This section introduces the key principles guiding the definition of the Commons, emphasising their role in aligning tools with shared standards and fostering adaptability for future needs. The following subsections explore the purpose and scope of the Commons, their defining features and aspects, and their critical relationships to the OSTrails Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture. Together, these elements provide a comprehensive understanding of what the Commons are, their intended impact, and how they function within the broader OSTrails ecosystem.

2.1. Purpose and Scope

The purpose of the Commons is to support the adoption of interoperability within the OSTrails ecosystem by providing reusable, adaptable, and tool-agnostic resources. These Commons is designed to enable seamless integration of tools while remaining flexible enough to accommodate diverse research contexts. Importantly, they are not limited to supporting tools currently within the OSTrails federation but extend their utility to tools outside the project and those that may emerge in the future. By offering a structured yet adaptable set of resources, the Commons aims to simplify adoption and foster interoperability across a wide range of stakeholders.

2.1.1. Supporting Adoption Without Bias

The Commons is **intentionally tool-agnostic**. Rather than prescribing specific low-level technological choices or other implementation details, they provide the foundational elements - such as shared data models, best practices, and specifications - that allow tools to integrate smoothly with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture. This neutrality ensures that the Commons can be adopted by a variety of tools, from those already in the federation to external platforms that may wish to adopt OSTrails standards. By offering suitable and adaptable resources, the Commons empowers developers to incorporate interoperability features while retaining the flexibility to address specific technical or organisational needs.

2.1.2. Broad and Inclusive Scope

While the Commons is closely tied to the OSTrails project, their scope extends well beyond its immediate boundaries:

- **Internal Support:** Within the OSTrails federation, the Commons provides tools and platforms with the necessary resources to align with the IF and RA. This ensures that all federation tools work seamlessly together, enhancing their collective impact.
- **External and Future Tools:** The Commons is designed to be shared beyond the federation, enabling external tools and future developments to benefit from established interoperability practices. This broader applicability ensures that the Commons contributes to global research ecosystems and remain relevant as new technologies and standards emerge.
- **Flexibility:** The Commons is as open as the Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture themselves, offering a high degree of flexibility in their application. Just as the IF and RA define the principles of interoperability without prescribing exact solutions or technologies, the Commons enables a wide range of tools to adopt best practices without being constrained by particular software, infrastructure, or technical choices.

At the same time, it is crucial to recognise what the Commons **does not**:

- **Make Interoperability Design Decisions:** The role of defining and governing interoperability lies with the OSTrails IF and RA. The Commons implements and support those decisions but do not replace their functions. In line with the IF/RA, the Commons can make well-justified technological choices in order to maximise the adoption support potential.
- **Directly Implement Features in Tools:** The development and integration of interoperability features are the responsibility of individual tools and platforms. The Commons provides the resources to guide and facilitate this process but do not undertake the implementation themselves.
- **Imply Unnecessary Governance or Policy Measures:** While the Commons provides frameworks for governance at a higher level (such as cross-project collaboration), the internal governance or policy frameworks for specific tools or platforms remain outside the Commons. Each tool or platform is responsible for managing its own governance, user policies, and operational procedures and the Commons should not be limiting in this sense in any way.

2.1.3. Clear Boundaries to Ensure Focus

By focusing on providing enabling resources rather than dictating design or implementation, the Commons maintains their adaptability and usefulness across a broad range of tools and contexts. This delineation of responsibilities ensures a clear division of roles:

- The **IF and RA** define the high-level interoperability standards and architecture.

- The **Commons** supplies the resources to support those standards and help tools to adopt them.
- The **tools and platforms** implement the interoperability features guided by these resources.

The Commons is designed to be a collection of interoperability-enabling resources that support IF/RA-adoption without dictating specific tools. They focus on providing shared specifications, best practices, reusable code, templates, and community frameworks, while leaving the detailed implementation decisions, tool-specific functionality, and interoperability architecture to the tools themselves and the broader OSTrails IF/RA. This clear separation ensures that the Commons remains a practical, flexible, and reusable resource while maintaining alignment with the project's broader goals.

2.2. Key Features and Aspects

The Commons is defined by a set of key features, criteria, and aspects that ensure they serve as effective, flexible, and sustainable resources for interoperability. These characteristics are foundational to their role in supporting seamless integration across tools within the OSTrails federation and beyond. Each feature not only enhances the usability and adoption of the Commons but also ensures that they remain relevant and adaptable to emerging technologies and evolving research needs. The following list outlines these essential features, along with explanations of their significance:

- **Tool-agnostic**

One of the core principles of the Commons is that they are tool-agnostic. This means the resources within the Commons are designed to be independent of specific tools, programming languages, or platforms. Naturally, technological decisions will have to be made; however, those will be guided by a proper analysis (such as D2.1) and/or best practices. By avoiding tool-specific dependencies, the Commons allows a diverse range of systems - both existing and future - to integrate seamlessly, regardless of their underlying technology stack. This agnosticism fosters broader adoption, enabling tools from different domains, environments, and technological ecosystems to benefit from various shared interoperability resources.

- **Open**

The Commons is open by design. They embrace open standards, open-source software, and transparent methodologies to ensure that all stakeholders - whether within the OSTrails project or outside it - can freely access, modify, and contribute to the resources. This openness supports collaboration and innovation, ensuring that the Commons remains adaptable to new needs and ideas. By adopting open practices, the Commons also align with the broader vision of open research, where accessibility and community-driven development are prioritised.

- **Evolving**

The evolving nature of the Commons ensures they remain flexible and adaptable over time. As new technologies, tools, and research practices emerge, the

Commons will continue to evolve to meet the changing needs of the research community. Another primary change driver for the Commons is the OSTrails Interoperability Framework which will evolve during the course of the project and may be further adjusted in the future beyond the project. This characteristic is crucial for long-term sustainability, as it allows the Commons to incorporate feedback from its users and stakeholders and to adapt to shifting standards and technological advances. The evolving nature also supports iterative development, meaning the Commons can be refined over time, ensuring continuous improvement and relevance.

- **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)**

The FAIR principles are fundamental to the design of the Commons. Each resource within the Commons should be created with a focus on making data and tools findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. This adherence to FAIR ensures that the resources are not only useful for immediate interoperability needs but are also structured in a way that promotes long-term usability and discovery. FAIR compliance helps foster a culture of open, transparent research, making it easier for researchers and developers to find and apply the tools and resources they need.

- **Transparent**

All resources within the Commons, from specifications to guidelines, are documented in a clear and accessible manner. Transparency ensures that stakeholders can understand the rationale behind each design decision, fostering trust and promoting wider adoption. It also encourages collaboration and accountability, as users can see how the resources evolve and contribute to ongoing improvements.

- **Sustainable**

Sustainability emphasises not only the long-term availability of the resources but also their ability to adapt to changing technological, organisational, and funding landscapes. The Commons is designed with sustainability in mind, incorporating practices that ensure they remain relevant, supported, and useful in the long run. This may involve fostering a vibrant community of contributors, maintaining and governing the Commons as a collection of various resources, and continuously aligning the Commons with evolving research practices and policies.

- **Inclusive**

The Commons is designed to be inclusive, supporting diverse stakeholders from various domains of research and across different geographical regions. By embracing inclusivity, the Commons ensures that tools, methodologies, and resources are accessible to all researchers, regardless of their background, expertise, or resources. This inclusivity extends to welcoming contributions from a wide array of stakeholders, ensuring the Commons evolves in ways that reflect the needs of the global research community.

- **Interoperable**

The Commons supports interoperability, and as such, the resources within the Commons are built to align with established interoperability standards, ensuring

that they integrate seamlessly with other tools and services within the OSTrails federation. By emphasising interoperability, the Commons enables a connected ecosystem where tools and data flow smoothly between different platforms, enhancing collaboration and supporting complex research processes.

- **Modular and Scalable**

The Commons is designed to be modular and scalable, meaning they can be used in different combinations depending on the needs of specific tools or research contexts. This modularity allows stakeholders to select only the relevant resources they need, avoiding unnecessary complexity. Furthermore, scalability ensures that as the number of tools, services, and research activities grows, the Commons can expand and evolve to support increased demand without sacrificing performance or usability.

The key features, criteria, and aspects of the Commons is designed to ensure that they are not only effective in supporting current tools and research initiatives but also adaptable to future developments. By being tool-agnostic, open, evolving, FAIR, transparent, sustainable, inclusive, interoperable, and modular, the Commons can provide lasting value across diverse research communities. These characteristics enable the Commons to serve as a flexible, collaborative, and sustainable resource that promotes widespread adoption of interoperability standards and practices across the global research ecosystem.

2.3. Relations to OSTrails IF and RA

The Commons, as a collection of reusable resources, work in close alignment with the broader OSTrails Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture, as well as the tools within the OSTrails federation. The primary purpose of the **Commons is to serve as a supporting layer** that facilitates the implementation of the IF and RA specifications in actual tools. These resources **provide flexible, modular building blocks** that tools can adopt based on their specific needs, while still ensuring overall alignment with the goals of the Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture.

The **OSTrails Interoperability Framework** provides the conceptual and technical definitions for achieving interoperability across various systems, offering **high-level guidance on data exchange standards, protocols, and methodologies**. Similarly, the **Reference Architecture** outlines how systems and tools should be structured and interact within a federated research environment. These documents set the foundational standards for achieving interoperability, but they do not dictate specific implementations of these principles. This is where the Commons comes into play: they offer **practical reusable resources** that allow tools to implement high-level definitions of the IF/RA efficiently and flexibly.

Tools within the OSTrails federation can directly implement the IF/RA by using the principles and guidelines provided within these documents (D1.4 and later in D1.5), or they can leverage the resources in the Commons. The Commons provides predefined templates, standards, reference models, and best practices that help tools integrate

interoperability features without having to start from scratch. This approach **provides flexibility and choice**, allowing tools to select the resources that best fit their specific needs, infrastructure, and goals.

Additionally, the Commons creates a pathway for a **feedback loop** between the tools and the broader OSTrails ecosystem. Tools that implement interoperability can feedback improvements or report issues based on their real-world experiences. This feedback helps evolve the Commons, making them even more useful and adaptable for future implementations. For example, a tool that encounters a challenge in adhering to a specific standard might suggest modifications to the corresponding resource in the Commons, improving it for all subsequent users. This process establishes a **combination of bottom-up and top-down** development, where top-level interoperability standards and reference architectures inform the Commons, while the actual implementation and tool-specific needs provide valuable bottom-up insights for refinement.

Figure 3 - Relations between OSTrails IF/RA, Commons, and Tools

Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between the OSTrails IF/RA, the tools, and the Commons. The IF/RA provides the high-level interoperability definitions, while tools either implement these directly or utilise the Commons resources to facilitate their own implementation. Feedback from tools informs ongoing improvements to the Commons, thus ensuring **continuous alignment and enhancement** of the interoperability framework. This feedback mechanism ensures that the Commons evolves in a way that is not only aligned with the IF/RA but also continuously refined through practical experiences and implementation challenges faced by the tools within the federation. It encourages **dynamic, ongoing collaboration between stakeholders**, ultimately fostering a more effective, scalable, and adaptable interoperability framework.

3. Structure of OSTrails Commons

The structure of the Commons is designed to provide a clear and scalable framework that organises the various resources supporting interoperability. These resources are composed of multiple **core components** based on the Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) Framework, which are essential building blocks for achieving interoperability across tools and services within the OSTrails federation. Additionally, the structure includes **layers of components** that further define the types of resources available and their intended uses, ranging from technical specifications and data models to documentation and APIs. Managing this structure is crucial to ensure the Commons and its resources evolve smoothly, remain consistent, and meet the needs of both current and future tools. This section will outline the core components, the layers that organise them, and how the Commons will be managed over time, including versioning and updates to maintain long-term sustainability.

3.1. Key Components

The Commons is fundamentally structured around the **Plan-Track-Assess Framework**, which clusters tools into **three primary categories: Data Management Plan (DMP) platforms, Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), and FAIR assessment tools**. These categories represent the core components of the Commons, as they encapsulate the primary interoperability challenges and opportunities within the federation. While other supporting tools exist within OSTrails, they predominantly serve to enhance connections to the PTA Framework and, therefore, indirectly contribute to one of these core components. In addition to these components, maintaining the alignment and interoperability between them is crucial. The Commons also include **cross-cutting resources** and a **management and governance component**, which ensure seamless collaboration, evolution, and sustainability of the Commons over time.

The Commons is organised into five components, ensuring comprehensive coverage of all included resources. Every resource, whether directly supporting interoperability or serving as foundational infrastructure, is categorised within this structure. This framework encompasses the core PTA-related elements, supporting tools, and essential management resources to maintain and evolve the Commons effectively. The five components are as follows (and visualized in **Figure 4**):

- **Data Management Plan (DMP) Platforms - DMP Commons**

DMP platforms form the foundation for planning and documenting the management of research data. These tools define how data will be collected, processed, and shared, adhering to FAIR principles. Resources in this component include templates, schemas, and workflows that standardise data management practices, making DMP platforms interoperable across systems. More specifically, according to DMP-IF as described in D1.4, this component includes:

- **OSTrails Application Profile (AP)** as a tailored extension of the RDA DMP Common Standard (DCS) for maDMPs will be designed to enhance interoperability while addressing various requirements (e.g. funders). Technically, the specification of the application profile will be done as prescribed by the DCS (which will support such extensions) and will be part of the Commons as the description of data structure.
- **maDMP API Specification** will build on top of the DSC and OSTrails AP and specify the operations and data exchange. We plan to materialize this in the form of OpenAPI specification (using the current version, currently v3.1.1). Again, this promotes adoption as OpenAPI specification not only documents the API but also provides a way to generate source code or other artifacts (e.g. tests) as well as check compliance.
- **Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) - SKG Commons**

SKGs facilitate the organisation, discovery, and linking of research outputs through structured semantic relationships. They provide the underlying infrastructure for representing research data, entities, and their interconnections. Resources in this component shall include ontologies, data models, and vocabularies that promote consistency and integration between DMP platforms and FAIR assessment tools.

 - **OSTrails SKG-IF** as an extension of the RDA SKG-IF will focus on Common Standard and Data Model extensions, resulting in a specification for data structures guiding the adoption.
 - **SKG-IF Common API** will be a specification of API following identified use cases and supporting relevant operators to guide the adoption and eventually also check compliance.
- **FAIR Assessment Tools - FAIR Commons**

FAIR assessment tools evaluate the degree to which research outputs adhere to FAIR principles. These tools use standard metrics and criteria to assess findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. The Commons shall provide evaluation rubrics, scoring systems, and integration guidelines to harmonise these assessments across tools and ensure they align with DMP and SKG practices and other relevant systems.

 - **FAIR Reference Model** is mainly described in D1.2 and is an important resource supporting the adoption of interoperability framework in its FAIR pillar as a specification of data structure on data, software, and conceptual levels with respect to FAIR assessment.
 - **Interface Descriptors** in the form of OpenAPI specification (v3) describe input/output for FAIR testing tools for interoperability according to the FAIR-IF of OSTrails.
- **Cross-Cutting and Supporting Resources**

The supporting resources in the Commons ensure tools can be integrated effectively and consistently. These include clear documentation, training

materials, and reusable APIs and libraries for technical implementation. Ontologies and schemas provide semantic alignment, while standardised templates and evaluation rubrics ensure consistency in data representation and FAIR assessments. These resources help tools adopt the Commons with ease and flexibility.

- **Management and Governance**

This final component provides the foundation for the sustainability and evolution of the Commons. Versioning policies and a transparent governance framework ensure that updates are coherent and inclusive. Feedback mechanisms allow continuous improvement based on practical use, while compliance monitoring ensures alignment with interoperability standards. Sustainability planning and community engagement ensure the Commons remains relevant and widely adopted over time.

Figure 4 - Components of OSTrails Commons

Interoperability between the components is critical for the success of the Commons. For example, DMP platforms must align with SKG ontologies to ensure that the data management plans can be seamlessly represented in knowledge graphs. Similarly, FAIR assessment tools should directly leverage outputs from DMP platforms and SKGs for consistent and accurate evaluations. This alignment will be supported with the layered approach across the three main components (DMP, SKG, FAIR).

3.2. Layers of Components

The Commons is organised into a layered structure that complements the core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR) and supporting tools. This approach ensures a systematic, modular framework where resources are categorised not only by their functional area but also by the type of technical or conceptual contribution they make. The layering enables consistency across components, promotes reusability, and supports the alignment of tools with the Interoperability Framework.

Each layer reflects a distinct aspect of resource organisation, whether it involves APIs for tool integration, data models for structured information exchange, or compliance mechanisms for evaluating adherence to the framework. This structure is designed to

remain extensible, allowing new layers to be introduced as needs evolve, especially in response to extensions or updates in the Interoperability Framework. Unlike the introduction of new components, which are tied to the PTA framework and thus less likely, additional layers may be necessary to address emerging interoperability requirements or technological advancements.

- **APIs**

APIs define the interaction mechanisms for tools and platforms, ensuring seamless communication within the federation. Widely adopted standards such as OpenAPI⁴ are commonly used, as highlighted in D2.1, offering consistent interface definitions and auto-generated documentation. For more specialised use cases, asynchronous communication protocols, like WebSockets or message queues, can also be incorporated. This layer is critical for integrating tools effectively while maintaining technical consistency across the Commons.

- **Data Models and Structures**

This layer includes resources like JSON schemas, RDF vocabularies, and other mechanisms that define and validate data formats. By aligning with the Interoperability Framework, data models ensure consistency and facilitate data exchange between tools. The standardised representation of data across the federation supports scalability and interoperability across diverse use cases.

- **Documentation and Experience Sharing**

Structured documentation ensures that tools can adopt and integrate Commons resources effectively. Resources in this layer include guidelines, implementation examples, and experience-sharing mechanisms, which help refine the Commons based on practical insights. This layer bridges the gap between theoretical specifications and real-world implementation, ensuring resources remain accessible and actionable.

- **Cross-Component Alignment**

Resources in this layer provide mechanisms for harmonising elements across components. Crosswalks, mapping guides, and alignment frameworks allow for reuse and compatibility between tools that might operate under different components. For example, aligning data models between DMP platforms and SKGs reduces redundancy and ensures smoother workflows across domains.

- **Testing and Validation**

This layer includes tools and methods to verify the robustness and correctness of Commons resources. Validation mechanisms for data models, conformance testing tools for APIs, and mock environments for testing integration scenarios are examples of resources here. These tools help maintain the quality and reliability of the resources within the Commons.

- **Compliance Checking**

⁴ <https://spec.openapis.org/>

Separate from testing, compliance check resources evaluate how well tools align with the Interoperability Framework. These might include rubrics, automated assessment tools, or guidelines for improving adherence. This layer supports continuous improvement of tools while preserving their flexibility in implementation.

By adopting this layered structure, the Commons provides a clear organisational framework that fosters alignment, consistency, and modularity. Layers serve as a bridge for cross-component collaboration, enabling tools to share resources or align workflows when needed. They also ensure that the Commons remains adaptable, as new layers can be introduced without disrupting existing resources.

Figure 5 - Layers and Components of OSTrails Commons

This extensibility is crucial for the long-term sustainability of the Commons. While the core components are closely tied to the PTA framework and less likely to change, the ability to add layers allows the Commons to evolve in response to updates to the Interoperability Framework or emerging needs within the research ecosystem. The (conceptual) **Figure 5** illustrates the components and their shared layers and provides a visual representation of this structure, emphasising the connections and flexibility inherent in the Commons design.

3.3. Managing Commons

Managing the Commons requires careful attention to software engineering principles, resource curation, and federation strategies. The Commons is a diverse set of resources, each potentially developed and versioned as a standalone project, brought together to form a curated and interoperable collection. This section explores the principles guiding their management, the challenges involved, and the structural implications for ensuring long-term sustainability and usability.

The management of the Commons is guided by several key principles that ensure its effectiveness and sustainability. These principles emphasise modularity, coordination, and adaptability to align with evolving standards and technologies while maintaining coherence across its components.

- **Separation of Concerns:** Resources are designed to be modular, enabling their independent development and evolution. This principle ensures that each resource focuses on a specific functionality, simplifying updates and minimising cross-impact among resources. Naturally and as in software engineering practice, resource can still relate via dependencies (ideally loose coupling); however, managing them separately is key for the maintainability.
- **Curated and Federated Approach:** Resources are developed collaboratively across different tools and projects but are curated centrally to maintain alignment and usability. This blend of decentralisation and centralised oversight fosters innovation while preserving consistency.
- **Versioning and Dependency Management:** Each resource is carefully versioned, with clear dependencies documented. This approach minimises conflicts when resources are updated or replaced and helps maintain compatibility across the Commons.
- **Sustainability through Adaptation:** Mechanisms are established to phase out obsolete components and integrate new ones in response to technological advancements or evolving user needs. The Commons evolves to remain relevant and effective.
- **Alignment with the Interoperability Framework:** All resources adhere to the standards and practices defined by the IF, ensuring compatibility across the federation of tools and platforms.

Several challenges arise in managing a collection as dynamic as the Commons. These challenges highlight the complexities of maintaining a curated and interconnected set of resources while addressing user and technological demands.

- **Dynamic Updates:** Frequent updates to resources demand mechanisms for seamless integration and careful assessment of impacts. Automated tools and clear workflows can help mitigate risks.
- **Obsolescence Management:** Resources may become outdated as standards evolve. A structured process for deprecating such resources ensures continuity for users while introducing improved replacements.
- **Interdependencies:** Resources often rely on others within the Commons, making it essential to document these relationships. This clarity prevents conflicts and supports smooth updates.
- **Curatorial Efforts:** Sustaining a high-quality collection requires ongoing review, alignment with user feedback, and updates. This effort ensures the Commons remains practical and widely adoptable.

To address these challenges, the structure of the Commons must support modularity, transparency, and user engagement. This structure enables users and contributors to navigate, adopt, and improve the resources effectively. There are related strategic and technical aspects for achieving well-maintained collection of resources:

- **Resource Registry:** A centralised catalogue provides metadata for each resource, including version numbers, descriptions, and dependencies. This registry serves as a single source of truth for users.
- **Version Control and Change Logs:** Every update is documented in detail, ensuring transparency and enabling users to track changes over time. This practice builds trust and facilitates troubleshooting.
- **Dependency Mapping:** Clear documentation of interdependencies among resources prevents conflicts and aids in compatibility assessments during updates.
- **Update Notification Systems:** Users/adopters are informed promptly about resource updates or deprecations, enabling them to adapt their workflows with minimal disruption.
- **Governance and Review Cycles:** Regularly scheduled reviews and updates ensure the Commons aligns with project objectives and user expectations. Feedback loops support iterative improvement.
- **Archival System:** Historical versions of resources are preserved, enabling legacy support, referencing via PIDs and providing context for decision-making processes.

To address the challenges of managing a dynamic and interconnected collection, the Commons relies on a structured approach that emphasizes transparency, modularity, and user engagement. The Commons as a centralized resource registry ensures consistency by cataloguing metadata, version histories, and dependencies. Clear documentation of interdependencies, combined with robust version control and change logs, minimizes conflicts and supports seamless updates. Regular governance cycles and user feedback loops drive iterative improvements, while archival systems preserve historical versions for legacy support and reference. These strategies collectively ensure that the Commons remains practical, sustainable, and responsive to evolving user and technological needs.

4. GORC Elements

The GORC (Global Open Research Commons) International Model, in our case in version 1.1⁵, provides a **comprehensive framework for defining the essential elements, categories, subcategories, attributes, and features of research commons**. The model is structured as a spreadsheet, offering a flat breakdown of the key components necessary for the development and evaluation of a commons, specifically within the context of research data and services. It is designed to serve as a flexible, non-prescriptive **guide that helps stakeholders from around the world align their efforts in creating interoperable and sustainable commons** for the public good. While the model emphasises inclusivity and best practices, it does not mandate any specific structure or implementation but rather **encourages consideration** of all elements, categorising them by their relevance at different stages of commons development.

In this section, we summarise the core elements of the GORC International Model, as adapted and applied to the Commons initiative. We have reviewed and incorporated the essential elements, categories, subcategories, and features defined in the GORC model, ensuring that our approach reflects the global vision while remaining adaptable to the specific needs of the OSTrails federation. Each core element is presented with relevant details, noting how we have considered both mandatory and optional components in line with the priorities set forth in the model. While the full breakdown and more detailed analysis of these elements can be found in the **attached spreadsheet (see Annex)**, this summary outlines our interpretation and alignment with the GORC framework, focusing on the most pertinent features for the OSTrails project.

The GORC model's focus on flexibility and adaptability makes it an ideal basis for developing the Commons structure that can evolve in response to the needs of a global and diverse community. As we move forward with the development of the Commons, we will continue to follow the principles of the GORC model (even though we acknowledge that **not all attributes and features are applicable to our case**), ensuring that each component is carefully assessed and integrated to create a coherent, sustainable, and interoperable resource for the OSTrails tools and future collaborators. The following sections provide a detailed look at each essential element of the GORC model as it pertains to the Commons, including the categories, subcategories, attributes, and features that define the resources and their relationships.

4.1. Governance and Leadership

This essential element of GORC outlines key principles and guidance for establishing effective governance structures as part of the OSTrails Commons. It emphasizes creating a robust framework that **clearly defines roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes, ensuring accountability and transparency** in the management of resources and operations. Governance structures are designed to support ethical,

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00119>

equitable, and inclusive practices, fostering collaboration and trust among stakeholders. A critical decision is to **embed adaptability into governance**, allowing the framework to evolve over time in response to the changing needs of the Commons and its community.

As part of this effort, **Commons Intent and Definition** has essentially now resulted in this deliverable document, providing a clear articulation of the Commons' purpose and foundational principles. **Commons Strategic Planning** ensures long-term alignment with the mission and values, guiding priorities for sustainable development. Additionally, Internal **Commons Policy Development, Implementation, and Review** establishes structured processes for creating, refining, and assessing policies that govern operations, resource management, and stakeholder engagement.

Key takeaways include the assignment of clear responsibilities for current operations and long-term sustainability, the prioritization of ethical stewardship, and the integration of inclusive leadership practices. Decisions such as promoting transparency, managing risks, and maintaining strategic alignment with the Commons' mission and values will guide its trajectory. Additionally, governance will focus on sustaining the Commons through **proactive leadership, regular evaluation, and alignment with global best practices** to ensure its relevance and resilience in the future.

4.2. Rules of Participation and Access

The concept of Rules of Participation and Access plays a vital role in shaping the community dynamics and governance of the OSTrails Commons. GORC emphasizes the need for clear policies that define who can participate in the commons and under what conditions, **ensuring that access and contributions are managed transparently and equitably**. In line with this guidance, the OSTrails Commons has established a strategic framework that governs participation, outlining the roles of both developers/maintainers and adopters, such as tool owners. These community members will have **defined rights and obligations, ensuring a collaborative and sustainable environment** where contributors shape the evolution of the commons while benefiting from the resources it provides.

The guidance from GORC has been instrumental in defining the policies for access, reuse, attribution, and acceptable use within OSTrails Commons. These policies will be publicly available in the Commons' repository, accompanied by the resources list and relevant documentation. By including essential policies, such as the Access Policy, Reuse Policy, and Privacy Policy, OSTrails Commons aims to provide a clear structure for how resources are accessed, shared, and reused, aligning with intellectual property rights, licenses, and the commons' overall values (via **LICENSE and contributing guidelines**). The open and transparent approach ensures that contributors understand their responsibilities and the terms of their participation. Furthermore, the inclusion of a **Code of Conduct**, based on the Covenant Contributor guidelines, ensures that community engagement remains respectful, collaborative, and aligned with best practices in similar open, technical projects. This approach not only fosters trust but also promotes long-term sustainability and growth of the OSTrails Commons as a community-driven resource.

4.3. Sustainability

Currently, the sustainability aspects are addressed within the OSTrails project but will require **continued effort and development beyond the project's conclusion**. Key to the success of the commons will be ensuring adaptability and scalability as it matures from a minimal viable plan to a fully-fledged, sustainable platform. Moreover, the stewardship of research objects, services, and tools will focus on maintaining integrity, accessibility, and usability over time, through proper metadata, documentation, and contextualization.

Transition plans will be developed to ensure continuity, even in the event of ceasing certain services or tools, while scalability plans will be in place to accommodate growth in both funding and demand. **Building and maintaining community trust will be essential**, and this will be achieved through transparent governance, equitable participation, and engagement strategies, all supported by clear KPIs and metrics. Beyond the OSTrails project, the commons must **transition to a community-driven effort**, with tools and resource owners actively contributing to and curating the commons, developing new resources, enhancing existing ones, and aligning the work with future projects. This will ensure the long-term success and relevance of the OSTrails Commons as a shared resource for the research community.

4.4. Engagement

OSTrails Commons' engagement strategy is currently managed within the project, ensuring **suitable and consistent communication** about its structure, services, and decision-making processes. Clear and accessible content is shared through platforms such as social media, blogs, newsletters, and events like hackathons and strategic meetings (such as national and thematic pilots' meetings). These updates, shared periodically, are aimed at users, providers, and researchers to maintain community involvement. Transparent, publicly documented processes are in place to **ensure accountability to stakeholders, including the sharing of training materials and decision-making procedures**. Culturally appropriate materials and translations are provided to ensure inclusivity.

Community input will be actively encouraged through **structured feedback mechanisms typical for similar projects** (GitHub Issues and Discussions). Contributions are acknowledged, and feedback is used to inform future decisions. To incentivize participation, the project **focuses on reducing barriers to engagement** (and adoption of OSTrails IF). OSTrails Commons also shall engage with other research commons, infrastructure hosts, institutions, and funders, with plans for further collaboration. This engagement will be crucial for future adoption and community building and will help expand outreach to initiatives like the Research Data Alliance.

4.5. Human Capacity

Currently, the human capacity of OSTrails Commons **is managed within the project**, with roles assigned to staff and contractors. In the future, responsibility for maintaining individual resources will shift to the resource maintainers. **Credit for contributions and maintenance will be transparently acknowledged.** Regular reviews and clear documentation will ensure **effective management of personnel**, fostering a positive and well-organized community.

The OSTrails Commons will leverage **widely adopted technologies** to simplify the management and delivery of services, ensuring sustainability. **Detailed and user-centred documentation will help guide contributors** and ensure accessibility, with feedback playing a key role in refining user experiences. Clear contributing guidelines will be provided for **maintainers**, who will also be responsible for clarifying any uncertainties and guiding others on how to contribute and maintain the commons effectively.

4.6. Interoperability

OSTrails Commons addresses the "Interoperability" essential element through a multi-faceted approach that ensures seamless integration across technical, organizational, and legal dimensions. For technical interoperability, we **provide guidance** on evolving APIs, data formats, and semantic standards to facilitate the exchange of research objects. This includes adopting interoperable file formats and ensuring that APIs align with community standards. In terms of organizational interoperability, we encourage collaboration with other commons, repositories, and research institutions, aligning business processes and goals to ensure mutual benefit. We also promote legal **interoperability by requiring open, permissive licensing** for all research objects and tools, which will be clearly specified in the metadata and harmonized to minimize legal conflicts and ensure broad reuse. The commons will provide guidance for tool developers to maintain compatibility with these interoperability standards. Furthermore, **English is the primary language** for documentation, services, and tools, while additional languages may be included as appropriate. These measures, alongside clear **LICENSE and contributing guidelines**, ensure transparent and accessible participation in the commons, fostering long-term sustainability and compatibility across various research ecosystems.

4.7. Standards and Conventions

OSTrails Commons will focus on the sustainability and adaptability of its standards, conventions, and guidelines by closely monitoring and adopting community-supported updates. These standards will be applied across research objects, services, tools, and metadata to ensure compatibility and maintain relevance within the evolving research ecosystem. The Commons will provide clear protocols for **cataloguing and sharing resources**, supporting the integration of research objects as part of the broader resource collection, and emphasizing interoperability across systems.

To promote consistency, OSTrails Commons will adhere to established metadata standards that enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and reusability of resources, particularly research software and collections. Metadata will be structured using standardized formats and controlled vocabularies, ensuring **machine-actionable and interoperable data**. The commons will also adopt quality standards to ensure "fitness for purpose," providing **clear guidelines and validation processes** to foster high standards of completeness, accuracy, and consistency. Additionally, PID infrastructure will be used to track and manage assets, with **integration to services like Zenodo** for issuing PIDs for the Commons. This will support long-term sustainability and ensure assets are easily discoverable across platforms.

4.8. ICT Infrastructure

The ICT Infrastructure essential element highlights that while some infrastructure categories are **not directly relevant to OSTrails Commons**, as it is primarily a curated collection of resources rather than a standalone infrastructure platform, the review process has still been valuable. OSTrails Commons will be represented in both **human-readable formats** (via documentation and additional information) and **machine-actionable formats** (through hosting on open-source-friendly platforms like GitHub and ReadTheDocs). These services support interoperability and ensure accessibility for the community.

The decision not to host dedicated ICT infrastructure for OSTrails Commons reinforces its distributed and scalable design, enabling the collection to grow or adapt without significant concerns about infrastructure constraints. The evaluation confirmed that **using GitHub and ReadTheDocs aligns with the goals of open access and public contribution**, ensuring that the selected services are suitable for facilitating the Commons' mission of promoting resource interoperability. This approach ensures that the project remains lightweight, flexible, and community-focused while maintaining adherence to standards and best practices.

4.9. Services and Tools

OSTrails Commons functions primarily as a **catalogue, linking users to external resources, services, and tools rather than directly providing them**. It ensures the maintenance and sustainability of this catalogue by establishing processes for periodic assessments, focusing on the accessibility, functionality, and other qualities of the listed resources. While the Commons support metadata harvesting and facilitates discoverability, it does not directly manage or host research objects, tools, or data services. Responsibility for the **maintenance, quality control, and FAIR** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) compliance of these research objects rests with the individual resource providers.

To support the broader research ecosystem, the Commons facilitate access to key external services, including Research Object Repositories for structured storage and sharing, Discovery Services for enhanced findability, Persistent Identifier Services such as

DOIs and ORCID for reliable attribution, and Vocabulary and Semantic Object Services to improve interoperability and metadata quality. These integrations ensure that research objects are more easily identified, evaluated, and connected within the scholarly landscape.

The Commons **promote best practices for using external tools**, services, and standards, reinforcing the adoption of **persistent identifiers like DOIs for releases and ORCID for contributor credit**. It provides an open, searchable catalogue of external services, ensuring quality assurance through functional, performance, and security testing. Clear documentation and service-level policies are made available to users. Support is facilitated through the respective service providers, with general assistance provided via **GitHub issues and discussions** for the Commons itself.

4.10. Research Objects

OSTrails Commons will include a variety of resources, such as research objects and other digital objects **related to research publications**. These resources will be guided to become easily accessible and reusable (incl. relevant publications and crediting authors). The commons will **support the discovery and integration of these resources**, facilitating their use across different research tools. Additionally, we plan to promote OSTrails Commons within the research community to encourage its adoption and use.

4.11. KPIs and Metrics

A dedicated section on KPIs and Metrics highlights that while the OSTrails Commons team has considered the importance of establishing measurable outcomes, the current focus is on **internal project KPIs and metrics** specific to the development phase. These internal measures are tailored to track progress, ensure resource quality, and guide the initial curation of the Commons.

As OSTrails Commons evolves, additional KPIs and metrics will be developed to reflect its operational goals and community impact. Due to the technically oriented and highly specific nature of the Commons, many standard KPIs from broader frameworks are not directly applicable. However, the **development of tailored metrics to measure resource usability, interoperability, and user engagement** will be a priority to ensure the Commons meets its intended purpose and serves the needs of its community effectively.

5. Technical Realisation

The Commons will be managed as an open-source project, ensuring flexibility, transparency, and active community collaboration. By following established best practices for open-source software development, the Commons will evolve in a structured, scalable manner, offering both human-readable and machine-actionable resources. The project will be hosted on GitHub, with automated processes in place to maintain consistency and quality across all resources.

5.1. Representing the Collection

To effectively represent the Commons as a collection of interconnected resources, a standardised approach will be adopted that integrates both machine-actionable and human-readable formats. The aim is to ensure that the Commons can be easily navigated, understood, and utilised by various stakeholders, including developers, researchers, and tool implementers.

- **Structured Metadata:** Each resource in the Commons will be accompanied by metadata that describes its purpose, scope, version, dependencies, and usage guidelines. This metadata will be standardised to ensure that it is easily discoverable and interoperable with other resources. A JSON or YAML schema will be adopted for this purpose, making it straightforward for tools and services to consume and process the metadata.
- **Index and Catalogue:** A central index or catalogue will be developed, listing all available resources in the Commons, along with relevant metadata, links to documentation, and associated versions. This catalogue will serve as a directory for stakeholders to find relevant resources quickly. It will also be designed to support search and filtering, making it easier to locate specific components, such as tools related to DMP, SKG, or FAIR assessments.
- **Interlinking of Resources:** To ensure the interconnectedness of the resources in the Commons, the metadata for each resource will include references to other relevant resources. For example, a DMP tool might link to relevant SKG or FAIR tools, enabling users to easily navigate the relationship between components. This interlinking will also provide insight into how resources are used together, facilitating the development of interoperable toolchains.
- **Human-Readable Documentation:** The collection will be represented on ReadTheDocs with human-readable documentation for each resource. This documentation will clearly describe the functionality, usage, and potential integrations of the resource, making it easier for end-users and developers to understand its value and how to incorporate it into their work. Documentation will be continuously updated as the resources evolve, ensuring that it accurately reflects the current state of the Commons.
- **Versioning and Compatibility:** To represent the evolution of the Commons, versioning will play a central role. Each release of a resource will be versioned, and

the catalogue will highlight the versions of resources that are compatible with each other. A visual timeline or changelog may be created to show how resources have evolved over time and which versions are currently active or deprecated.

By taking this comprehensive approach to representing the collection, the Commons will ensure that users can easily find, use, and contribute to the resources, all while maintaining clarity, interoperability, and sustainability.

5.2. Open-Source Project

The Commons will be structured as a well-defined open-source project, bringing together a collection of diverse resources and ensuring their FAIRness⁶ and quality⁷.

- **Public and Open Access:** Use of publicly accessible repositories (see Section 5.3).
- **Versioning and Releases:** Semantic versioning (or an alternative versioning scheme where applicable) will be applied to ensure compatibility and maintain a clear history of changes. Releases will be tagged appropriately, allowing users to track updates, changes, and new features.
- **Licensing:** Open-source licences such as MIT or Apache 2.0 will be used for the Commons itself, with each resource potentially adopting its own licence (as long as it is compatible with the Commons' overall open philosophy).
- **Indexing and PIDs:** Repository contents will be registered in a community registry, such as Zenodo (through integration, getting PID record).
- **Promoting Citation:** Citation of code will be supported via the use of CodeMeta and/or Citation File Format files (see also Section 5.5).
- **Machine-Actionable Collection:** Resources in the Commons will be organised and versioned in a machine-readable format, allowing automated processing, discovery, and integration with tools. This structure will be aligned with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework, making it easier for tools and platforms to adopt and use relevant resources.
- **Quality Assurance Mechanisms:** External (automatic) quality assessments will be used resulting in the display of quality badges (see also Section 5.6).
- **Standard Project Metadata:** Standard files such as README.md, LICENSE, and CONTRIBUTING.md will be maintained for clarity and transparency in the open-source process, guiding both developers and end-users.

This approach ensures that all resources are curated, standardised, and ready for integration into tools, research workflows, or other services in a manner consistent with software engineering practices.

⁶ <https://fair-software.nl/>

⁷ Maintained using available SQAaaS platforms/services

5.3. GitHub Repositories

The OSTrails Commons will be hosted as an open-source project within a dedicated GitHub repository, serving as a **centralized index and collection of resources rather than directly hosting the resources** themselves. GitHub (github.com) provides a **transparent and collaborative environment** that supports version control, clear history tracking, and efficient testing workflows, ensuring the integrity and quality of the resources. Each resource in the Commons will remain in **its own repository or other appropriate hosting platform (if needed)**, ensuring flexibility and autonomy for resource maintainers. This approach allows individual resources to be independently developed, maintained, and updated while being seamlessly integrated into the Commons through the index.

- **Decentralized Resource Hosting:** Resources will remain in their own repositories or platforms, allowing specialized maintainers to oversee them independently.
- **Centralised Collection Index:** The GitHub repository for the Commons will act as an organized catalog, linking to resources, documentation, and related metadata.
- **Version Control and Traceability:** The GitHub repository ensures the collection itself is versioned and transparent, with a clear history of updates to the index and related files.
- **Collaboration and Testing:** GitHub's collaborative tools, such as issue tracking and pull requests, provide mechanisms to maintain the quality and relevance of the Commons' index.

OSTrails Commons will promote best practices across the resources, such as quality assurance, interoperability, and citable outputs, across the collection while leveraging the strengths of decentralized resource management. This distributed model ensures scalability, resilience, and broad participation, aligning with the principles of open-source development.

5.4. ReadTheDocs Static Pages

To complement the machine-actionable aspects of the Commons, a **human-readable documentation layer** will be provided via ReadTheDocs (readthedocs.org). It will make the Commons easily accessible, ensuring that users can quickly find the information they need while maintaining alignment with the overall vision and goals of OSTrails.

- **Visual Consistency:** The documentation will be designed to maintain a consistent visual style that aligns with the OSTrails project's branding and outputs, providing a seamless experience for users and contributors.
- **Versioned Documentation:** The documentation will follow the same versioning system as the resources in the Commons. Users will be able to reference specific versions of documentation that correspond to the resources they are using, ensuring consistency across implementations.
- **Clear and Structured Guides:** Clear guides for developers, tool implementers, and researchers will be provided, describing how to use, integrate, and contribute

to the Commons. This will include API documentation, data models, and integration instructions.

5.5. Support for Contributions

The Commons will be developed in a collaborative, community-driven manner. To support this, clear contribution guidelines and processes will be established, allowing both internal and external contributors to effectively engage with the project.

- **Contributing Guidelines:** A CONTRIBUTING.md document will outline how users can get involved in the project, from bug fixes to submitting new resources.
- **Issue and Pull Request Templates:** Custom issue and pull request templates will streamline contributions, ensuring that all necessary information is provided for efficient review. These templates will guide contributors to submit well-defined requests and help maintain consistency across the development process.
- **Code of Conduct:** A code of conduct will be established to foster a welcoming, respectful, and productive community environment. This will ensure that all contributors feel comfortable participating in discussions and development. Verified practices such as Contributor Covenant (contributor-covenant.org) in CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md file will be applied to ensure consistency.
- **Attribution:** Contributors will be recognised for their efforts in a standard way (CodeMeta, CONTRIBUTORS.md, and/or CITATION.cff), with acknowledgments included in documentation and credits on relevant resources.

By providing clear and structured avenues for contributions, the Commons will encourage active participation and ensure the project remains sustainable and collaborative over time.

5.6. Automated Tasks

To ensure high-quality development and timely maintenance, a robust set of automated tasks will be implemented using Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD) pipelines. By automating the following tasks, the project can maintain a high level of quality while reducing manual effort and ensuring that resources remain consistent, up-to-date, and compatible with each other.

- **Automated Testing:** The CI pipeline will automatically run unit tests, integration tests, and other checks to ensure that resources and documentation meet the required standards.
- **Dependency Management:** Suitable tools such as Dependabot will monitor dependencies across the project, ensuring that updates are automatically suggested and applied when necessary. This helps to keep the Commons aligned with the latest versions of required libraries and frameworks.
- **Code Style and Linting:** The CI pipeline will also verify compliance with established code style guidelines and run linters to ensure consistency and readability across code contributions.

- **Documentation Validation:** The CI pipeline will ensure that the documentation is up-to-date and accurately reflects the state of the resources in the Commons. This includes checking that all links are valid and ensuring that content adheres to predefined templates and guidelines.
- **Quality Assurance:** Use of Quality Gates and a fail-fast approach, via tools such as SonarQube.

6. Implementation Plan

The development of the Commons will be an ongoing, iterative process, closely aligned with the progression of the Interoperability Framework and Reference Architecture, as well as the tools within the OSTrails federation. Although the first formal release of the Commons is scheduled for Deliverable 2.6 in month 24, the foundation will be laid much earlier, beginning with Deliverable 1.4 (month 12), which marks the completion of the initial IF/RA. The Commons will evolve in tandem with the tools and IF/RA, with releases tied closely to the software development cycle and tool federation progress.

1. **OSTrails Commons Specification** (months 8-12)
2. **Initial Preparations and Setup** (months 12-14)

The initial phase will focus on laying the groundwork for the Commons, ensuring that necessary infrastructure, frameworks, and documentation are in place.

- a. **Repository and Infrastructure Setup:** The GitHub repository for the Commons will be established within the OSTrails organisation. The repository will serve as the central location for resource management, documentation, and collaborative development. During the first 12 months, this repository will be populated with initial resources, ensuring a clear organisation based on core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR) and supporting resources.
 - b. **DMP, SKG, FAIR Commons Definition:** Initial Commons will be defined for each of the core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR). This will include identifying the specific resources to be included in the Commons, as well as guidelines for their representation, versioning, and documentation. These frameworks will evolve in parallel with the development of the IF/RA, ensuring they align with the project's ongoing work.
 - c. **Initial Documentation and Guideline Creation:** A foundational README file will be created to outline the purpose, structure, and goals of the Commons. Initial guidelines for contributing, versioning, and maintaining resources will be established. Documentation for the core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR) will be developed, serving as a starting point for future contributions and resource integration.
 - d. **Interoperability Framework Alignment:** As Deliverable 1.4 (initial IF/RA) is also finalised by month 12, the first set of resources for the Commons will be aligned with the initial IF/RA. This alignment will ensure that the Commons meets interoperability requirements, and that the resources are usable for the tools and platforms within the OSTrails federation.
3. **Iterative Development and Integration with Tools** (months 14-20)

After the completion of the initial IF/RA, the development of the Commons will proceed iteratively, with ongoing refinement of resources and alignment with tools and frameworks.

 - a. **Refinement Based on Feedback:** As tools within the OSTrails federation begin to use the initial resources, feedback will be collected and used to

refine the resources and improve their compatibility and usability. These updates will be incorporated into the Commons repository, ensuring that the resources remain responsive to the evolving needs of the tools and platforms.

- b. **Versioning and Updates:** Versioning will be essential to ensure that resources are clearly identified and compatible with tools. The first formal version of the Commons will be released as part of Deliverable 2.6 (month 24), but iterative updates will be made throughout this phase based on tool integration and ongoing feedback. Resources will be versioned based on their stability and compatibility.
- c. **Cross-Component Alignment:** As the Commons evolves, maintaining alignment across the core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR) will be a priority. Cross-component alignment ensures that resources from different components can work together seamlessly. For example, alignment between DMP specifications and SKG data models will be prioritised.

4. **Pre-Release and Tool Integration** (months 20-22)

In months 18-24, the Commons will be more mature, with several components and resources ready for integration and wider testing across the OSTrails federation.

- a. **Testing:** During this phase, tools within the federation will continue to test and integrate the Commons resources. New resources will be added to the Commons, and existing ones will be updated based on testing feedback. This testing phase will ensure that the resources are fully aligned with the requirements of the tools and stakeholders.
- b. **Refinement of Resources:** Based on feedback from the beta testing, adjustments and refinements will be made to the Commons resources. These updates will be incorporated into the repository, and the documentation will be refined to reflect real-world usage and feedback from contributors.
- c. **Final Documentation:** Comprehensive documentation for all resources will be finalised. This will include detailed usage instructions, example use cases, and information about compatibility and versioning. Documentation will also include information on how to contribute to the Commons, and how to use the resources in tools and other systems.

5. **First Formal Release** (month 23-24)

The first formal release of the Commons will be made available as part of Deliverable 2.6. This release will include:

- a. **Stable Set of Resources:** A stable set of resources for each of the three core components (DMP, SKG, FAIR) will be available. These resources will be ready for integration with tools and other systems, and they will be fully documented with versioning information.
- b. **Public Access:** The GitHub repository will be publicly accessible, allowing stakeholders from within and outside the project to access, review, and contribute to the resources in the Commons. Transparency and openness

will be a key focus, and contributors will be encouraged to improve and extend the resources over time.

- c. **Sustainability and Maintenance Plan:** A sustainability plan will be put in place to ensure the continued development and maintenance of the Commons beyond the first formal release. This plan will outline governance, maintenance, and future development processes, ensuring that the Commons remains a valuable resource long-term.

6. **Post-Release and Continuous Improvement** (beyond month 24)

Even after the first formal release, the work on the Commons will continue, with an ongoing focus on expanding the collection of resources, improving their quality, and integrating new tools and frameworks.

- a. **Continuous Updates:** As the tools in the OSTrails federation evolve, and as new tools are integrated into the project, the Commons will be updated to reflect these changes. New resources will be added, and existing resources will be updated to ensure that they continue to meet the needs of the tools and stakeholders.
- b. **Feedback Loop:** The Commons will remain open to feedback from the community. Contributions from tool developers, researchers, and other stakeholders will be essential to ensure that the Commons remains relevant and useful. The iterative process of feedback and refinement will continue after the first formal release.
- c. **Long-Term Sustainability:** The long-term sustainability of the Commons will be ensured through ongoing governance, active community engagement, and periodic updates. This will allow the Commons to evolve alongside the OSTrails federation and continue to support interoperability across a wide range of tools and platforms.

By following this phased, iterative approach, the Commons will provide a solid foundation for tool interoperability and integration, while remaining flexible enough to evolve and expand as the needs of the project and its stakeholders change over time.

7. Conclusions

This document serves as the specification for the Commons, outlining its core components, features, and governance principles, as well as its alignment with the Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model. It provides a comprehensive framework that will guide the development of the commons, focusing on its role in supporting interoperability and fostering the adoption of tools within the OSTrails project and beyond. The document specifies the key aspects of the commons, such as its tool-agnostic nature, support for FAIR principles, and sustainable management practices.

The realisation of the Commons will unfold in the coming months based on the plan outlined in this document. The first release of the commons, as described in Deliverable 2.6, is scheduled for month 24, but its development will be iterative and closely tied to the progress of the tools in the OSTrails federation and their ongoing software releases. The detailed implementation of the commons will be guided by the principles and structure defined here, with continuous feedback and adaptation to ensure that it meets the evolving needs of the research community and aligns with the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (IF) and Reference Architecture (RA).

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9. Annex

- **GORC IM v1.1 table** (D2.5_OSTrails_Commons_Specification_GORC-IM-V1.1.xlsx)